

COGNITIVE CYNICISM AND ITS EFFECT ON EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT IN THE FOOD, BEVERAGE, AND TOBACCO SECTOR IN RIVERS STATE

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Organizational support and the quality of subordinate-supervisor relationships play a critical role in shaping employees’ perceptions of their workplace. Positive interactions, characterized by mutual support, recognition, and fair rewards, can reduce negative feelings such as mistrust, anger, and cynicism among employees. Supervisors provide guidance, resources, and incentives, while subordinates contribute their expertise, loyalty, and effort, creating a reciprocal relationship that strengthens organizational functioning.</p> <p>This study examines the impact of cognitive cynicism on employee commitment within the food, beverage, and tobacco sector in Rivers State, Nigeria. Drawing on the distinction between affective, continuance, and normative commitment, the research highlights that employees with affective commitment—those who genuinely desire to belong—are less prone to cynicism and more likely to engage positively with organizational objectives. Conversely, employees whose commitment is primarily continuance-based—driven by necessity or lack of alternatives—exhibit higher levels of cynicism, which may undermine workplace engagement and reduce overall commitment.</p> <p>By analyzing the interplay between cognitive cynicism and commitment types, the study provides insights into how organizational support mechanisms and effective supervisor-subordinate relationships can mitigate negative attitudes, enhance employee dedication, and promote sustainable organizational performance. The findings emphasize the importance of fostering a supportive work environment, recognizing employee contributions, and aligning reward systems with intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors to reduce cynicism and strengthen commitment.</p>	<p>Cognitive cynicism; Employee commitment; Organizational support; Supervisor-subordinate relationship; Workplace behavior</p>

INTRODUCTION

Organizational support and subordinate-supervisor relationship can create a good platform on which the workers view their employing organization. These shared relationships through support may reduce their ill feelings, anger and thoughts of mistrust. In the workplace, the supervisor provides a subordinate with support and monetary

rewards while in exchange, the subordinate contributes personal devotions and expertise (Wang, Liao, Xia, & Chang, 2010). Wang, Ma & Zhang (2014), states that employees who want to belong to the organization (affective commitment) might be more likely than those who need to belong (continuance commitment) or feel obliged to belong (normative commitment) to make an effort on behalf of the organization. Wang, Ma & Zhang (2014) asserted that cynicism in organizations is more displayed by employees who have continuance commitment.

Researchers have indicated the several factors which affect employee commitment as job security, compensation, and rewards (Hosseini, Mohammad, Bitar, Fariba, and Hosseinali, 2012). Employee' commitment in an organization is of great importance because it reflects upon performance in terms of maintaining the profit made by the company. With the persistent emphasis on accountability and attainment of organizational objectives by employees in organizations, foods, beverages and tobacco companies seek to have an organization in which workers are much more committed as they believe their institutions are safe, cynicism free, stable and relatively proactive to respond to changes. Having the ability to precisely determine the factors that influence the attainment of such commitment state is determined by the nature of the employees (Siccone, 2012) and their backgrounds.

The time when people were largely self-supporting, without organizations to take care of their wants and needs, seems long gone. People no longer provide for their own food, housing, footwear and clothing, health care, education and other vital and less vital products and services. Over time, more and more of these activities have been taken over by our employing organizations and, not surprisingly, these organizations have become central to our lives. It is obvious, then, that organizational effectiveness and the motivation and engagement of the persons working to accomplish that effectiveness are of paramount importance (Naus, Iterson & Roe, 2007). If organizations only consider the productivity and disregard human behaviors and sentiments, then it is unavoidable for the employees to feel unsafe and to develop negative attitudes and sentiments towards the organization itself. The work of Yousaf, Sanders, & Abbas (2018) proposed that different opinions on the task can appear from organizational roles and personality stereotypes. This may create a tension and provide a basis of cynicism between groups within the organization, and between the employee and the organization. Jehn and Mannix (2001) proposed that intense challenges in opinions between workers can decrease their level of trust for the organization, which may trigger cynicism in them.

Simha, Elloy, & Huang (2014) assert that if individuals get burned out from their jobs, they are likely to harbour negative attitudes toward their organizations, and also display behaviours that are disparaging to others giving rise to the problem of organizational cynicism which is detrimental to the organization. Individuals in the fast moving consumer goods companies who are cynical can influence their entire organizations and can prevent the organization from achieving its set goals (Nafei, 2013). Foods, beverages and tobacco employees exhibit cynical behaviours which affects the way service is delivered in these organizations due to burn out from the demands of the job. In modern times, things have changed due to globalization, technological factors, and diversity in the work place, thus foods, beverages and tobacco companies are faced with the enormous challenges of maintaining high service standards (Khan, 2014) and as such, preventing cynical feelings.

Foods, Beverages and Tobacco companies are those organizations or firms that deal on products that are sold quickly and at a relatively low cost. Examples of these products include and are limited to products such as packaged foods, beverages, tobacco, and other consumables. Foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Nigeria are in the state of hyper competition due to proliferation of brands in various categories. Foods, beverages and tobacco companies are an important segment of the retail sector of the Nigeria economy. However, studies available indicate that their performance has not been impressive. Rapid changes in technology, shortened product

life cycles, increased competitions owing to reduced barriers to international trade and globalization (Liu & Wang, 2013) have all contributed to the need for the companies to have distinctive capabilities or core-competence, which when successfully applied to the companies' markets become competitive advantages (Kim, Jung, Noh, & Kang, 2019). Many a time, most organizations do not achieve the level of marketing performance that will yield rents for them, hence some organizations experience sub-optimal or even out-right poor marketing performance. These high levels of competition has resulted in an increased degree of responsibilities for the employees in foods, beverages and tobacco companies, and as such, may lead to display of varying behaviours in relation to their organizational demands.

Over the years, researches done were limited to investigating the relationship of organizational cynicism on job burnout (Omoankhanlen & Oyam-Jajaboma, 2016), whereas, studies on employee commitment are mainly in relation to working conditions (Igbe, Okpa, & Aniah, 2017), organizational trust (Ozler & Atalay, 2011), and performance, but little or none has examined the influence of organizational cynicism on employee commitment. This gap in knowledge is also widened by the fact that less effort has been made for the identification of factors which may account for the positive and negative effect of commitment as it relates to the components cynicism in organizations. However, the studies on cynicism in companies are quite new and as such, this paper examined cognitive cynicism and employee commitment relationship on Foods, Beverages and Tobacco companies. Following the above stated relationship being investigated, the study was guided along these research questions; What is the relationship between cognitive cynicism and affective commitment in selected foods, beverage and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt?

What is the relationship between cognitive cynicism and normative commitment in selected foods, beverage and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt?

What is the relationship between cognitive cynicism and continuance commitment in selected foods, beverage and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt?

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework on Cognitive Cynicism and Employee Commitment

Source: Author's Desk Research, 2019.

LITERATURE REFLECTION Social Exchange Theory

Social exchange theory posits that all human relationships are formed by the use of a subjective cost-benefit analysis and the comparison of alternatives (Gould-Wiliams, 2007). It views social relations as an exchange process involving two steps. First, the actor's behaviour is contingent upon the reward from the environment; and second, the environmental reward is contingent upon the actor's behaviour (Blau, 1989). Based on this theory, it is contended that, positive organizational action (stimulus) that is perceived to be fair is the starting point for the

proposed model. Consequently, an employee would judge this action of “perceived fairness” by comparing the received output with comparable others (Gould-Wiliams, 2007). The theory views interpersonal interactions from a cost–benefit perspective, just like an economic exchange, except that a social exchange deals with the exchange of intangible social costs and benefits like respect, honor, friendship, and caring and is not governed by explicit rules or agreements (Akram, Afzal, & Ramay, 2019).

Social exchange theory is seen as a combination of conceptual models (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005) and this is the reason they all share a number of common features. “All social exchange theories treat social life as involving a series of sequential transactions between two or more parties” (Mitchell, Cropanzano, & Quisenberry, 2012, p. 21). “Resources are exchanged through a process of reciprocity, whereby one party tends to repay the good (or sometimes bad) deeds of another party” (Gergen, 1969, p. 33). Furthermore, it was noted that the link between the actor and the target may influence the quality of the exchange (Blau, 1964, p. 13). “Social exchange theory is one of the most enduring and widely used conceptual frameworks” (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005, p. 17).

The social exchange process “begins when an actor (eg. supervisor or co-worker), treats a target individual in a positive or negative fashion” (Eisenberger, Lynch, & Aselage, 2004, p. 14). These behaviours are called initiating actions, which may be positive (eg. Support or justice provision) or negative (eg. Abusive supervision, incivility and bullying) (Cropanzano & Rupp, 2008, p. 25). In response to these actions, the target may reciprocate with good or bad behaviors (Eisenberger,

Cotterell, & Marvel, 1987) which is called reciprocating responses. Social exchange theory proposes that “in reaction to positive initiating actions, targets will tend to reply in kind” (p. 14) which is classified into two types – relational responses and behavioral responses (Cropanzano & Rupp, 2008).

Cognitive Cynicism

This refers to lack of sincerity, honesty, and justice in the organization, where cognitive cynicism is accessible when staff feels that their corporation does not esteem their endeavours or care about every one of them, and therefore may be unlikely to make their best efforts for their corporation (Rehan, Iqbal, Fatima & Nawabl, 2017). Workers facing cognitive cynicism think that principles are often sacrificed for expedience, and that duality, guile, and personal interest are common in their firms (Rehan, Iqbal, Fatima& Nawabl, 2017). Bernerth, Armenakis, Field & Walker (2007) found that employees’ perceptions of cognitive cynicism are negatively associated with organizational commitment (Bernerth, Armenakis, Field & Walker, 2007). Similarly, Abraham indicated that cognitive cynicism reduces the performance in the organization (Abraham, 2000). Belief exists in societal norms and shapes socio-cultural and moral structure of society (Morgaan, 2005). The cognitive dimension which is the belief that emerges with negative emotions such as anger, condescension, and condemnation that the organization is not honest. Therefore, cynics believe that organizational practices are not fair, honest, and sincere, and they don’t trust their organizations (Brandes and Das, 2006). Cognitive dimension of organizational cynicism is referred as ideational approach based on the belief. In this context, worker think that organization do not keeps to fundamental principles like justice, honesty and sincerity in cognitive dimension of organizational cynicism (Dean at all., 1998). In this regard, the belief based on that there is unprincipled practices in organization has role on this cognitive approach (Pelit and Pelit, 2014). Cognitive organizational cynicism also shapes cynical attitudes or behaviors (Delken, 2004). Thus, there is a sceptic position that makes worker think altruistic actions or decisions related job process of organization service to create authority legitimacy and to preserve bureaucratic hierarchy (Dean at all., 1998; Goldner et al., 1977). Indeed, according to workers, manager or co-workers frequently tries to derive benefit via their behaviors seen as altruistic (Kanter and Mirvis, 1989). That is to say, it

is requested secret a goal in decisions and actions, which may affect workers negatively. It can be seen that some unprincipled practices like injustice, deceit and insincerity, gaining advantage, being unethical are routinized in cognitive organizational cynicism (Işık, 2014).

By cognitive cynicism, the employees that have experienced cynicism consider that the practices in the organizations are not based on principles and official declarations prepared by the organizations are not taken seriously by the employees. Besides, employees may be involved in such behaviors as lying, tricks and intrigue. Individual behaviors in the organization are thought to be inconsistent and unreliable according to the employees. The organizational relations are believed to be determined by self-interests. Thus, the employees can abandon such values as sincerity, honesty, trustworthiness for the sake of self-interests, therefore involving in immoral and corrupted attitudes (Brandes, 1997; Brandes and Das, 2006; Dean et al., 1998).

Employee Commitment

Employee commitment refers to the employee's emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organization. In essence, measuring employee commitment is an assessment of the congruence between an individual's own values and beliefs and those of the organization (Padala, 2011). Employee commitment is characterized as employees' willingness to contribute to organizational goals. When employees are sure that they will grow and learn with their current employers, their level of commitment to stay with that particular organization is higher (Opkara, 2004). In order to make employees satisfied and committed to their jobs, there is a need for strong and effective motivational strategies at various levels of the organization. Besides that, Ayeni and Phopoola (2007) have found a strong relationship between job satisfaction and employee commitment. According to them job satisfaction is mostly determine how well the organization meets employees expectations. On the other hand, Maxwell and Steele (2003) believed that the organization concerned on the look after employees' interest. It is clear, the higher the experience, the more positive the impact on the commitment. Further, an individual's experience with their co-workers had the impact on highly commitment to the organization (Maxwell and Steele, 2003). High level of employee commitment provide a clear focus for human resource manager on the grounds that commitment is in itself good and positive that should lead to high level of work performance. While according to Lok & Crawford (2001), a number of demographic variables, frequently included in this study.

Variables such as age (Mathieu and Zajac, 1990; Karadağ, Kılıçoğlu & Yılmaz, 2014; Williams and Hazer, 1986), organization tenure (Mathieu and Hamel, 1989; Mathieu and Zajac, 1990) and position tenure (Gregersen and Black, 1992; Mathieu and Zajac, 1990) have been found to be positively associated with organizational commitment. Mathieu and Zajac (1990) concluded that age is considerably more strongly related to attitudinal than to behavioral commitment.

Employee commitment is an important aspect in human resource management literature. It refers to the state in which employees sense loyalty with their respective organization and align themselves with organizational goals and objectives (Lambert, Hogan, & Griffin, 2007). The success of an organization depends on the commitment of employees toward the organization. Sinani (2016) argue that commitment towards an organization is more than just a formal membership but rather it encompasses the attitude to the organization and a willingness to pursue all things for the sake of the organization. Employees' commitment helps managers in programming, improving job performances and in decreasing frequency of absenteeism from duty (Somayyeh, Mohsen, & Zahed, 2013). On the other hand, having a committed staff provides a background for improvement and expansion of the organization, while the personnel with little or no commitment to the organization remain indifferent towards the

goals and overall success of the organization (Somayyeh, Mohsen, & Zahed, 2013). The fact that secondary schools and commercial banks are organizations, establishment of justice can be a significant action to improve job performance, efficiency, job satisfaction and organizational commitment in these organizations.

Gemlik, Sisman and Signri (2010) posit that employee commitment is a multidimensional construct where an individual feels psychologically bound to an organization. Lapointe & Vandenberghe (2018) also state that organizational commitment describes an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organization. This commitment is characterized by a strong belief in and acceptance of the organizations goals and values, a desire to exert considerable effort on behalf of the organization, and a strong desire to maintain membership in the organization (Lapointe & Vandenberghe, 2018). Organizational commitment according to Yahaya and Ebrahim (2016) is an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organization. If this association is positive then it fosters levels of personal and professional satisfaction and increased productivity.

Employee commitment is seen as an effective response to the whole organization and the degree of attachment or loyalty employees feel towards the organization (Ongori, 2007). Research within this perspective has tended to focus on individual differences as antecedents of commitment, revealing that factors such as age and organizational tenure are positively correlated with commitment, whereas level of education is negatively related (Aslam, Ilyas, Imran, & Rahman, 2016). Research utilizing this affective approach to commitment has also frequently revealed an inverse relationship between commitment and turnover intention (Gemlik, Sisman & Signri, 2010) as well as a positive relationship between commitment and regular employee attendance. Unfortunately, commitment has historically been found to exert little direct influence on actual work performance, although lessened turnover intention and consistent attendance are themselves critically important pro-organizational attitudes and actions (Mathieu & Zajac, 1990).

Successful strategy requires human commitment at the implementation stage. In addition, administrative support during the implementation phase of the strategy is crucial for success. Suwati and Gageh (2016), states that commitment is not only a concept of human relationships, but also the generation of human energy and the activation of human mind. Samson, Waiganjo and Koima (2015) argue that it is difficult to implement new ideas and initiatives without commitment. This requires the employee's commitment to coordinate strategy implementation and strategic decisions. Wnuk (2017) a recent Indonesian studies show that many companies do not prioritize the use of their employees' responsibilities as part of a strategy to improve their efficiency and competitiveness.

The characteristics from the definitions of employee commitment imply according to Sinani (2016) that the members of an organization wish to be active players in the organization and have an impact on what is going on in it, feel that they have high status within it, and are ready to contribute beyond what is expected of them. According to Dixit and Bhati (2012) commitment comes into being when a person, by making a side bet, links extraneous interests with a consistent line of activity. Employee commitment has an important place in the study of organizational behaviors since previous studies have found relationships between employee commitment and attitudes and behaviors in the workplace (Yucel, McMillan & Richard, 2014).

Conceptually, employee commitment is an important concept in both psychology and management literature. Colquitt, Lepine and Wesson (2011) define employee commitment as the desire on the part of an employee to remain a member of the organisation. It could also refer to the state in which people sense loyalty with their respective organisations, align themselves with organisational goals and value it (Fang, 2001; Aydin & Akdag,

2016; Lambert, Hogan & Graffin, 2007). Commitment is an attitude that reflects the extent to which an individual identifies with an organisation, is committed to its goal, and wishes to maintain membership in the organisation (Robbins, 2005). The degree at which an employee goes about delivering his/her duties and roles in the organisation amount to a great extent on what the organisation achieves. Doing these means that the employee is likely gratified with what he/she does in the organisation which may result from higher pay, better welfare packages, good leadership style, team work, good working condition and others

(Ugwu, 2000). Commitment is defined as the connection between the organization and the employees. It is also described as willingness and steady forces that determines and maintains the attachment of an individual to a particular organization (Spanuth, & Wald, 2017). In other words, it is a psychological bond that is characterized by the members' feeling of attachment, obligation, and loyalty to a given organization. Commitment also describes the level of employees' acceptance of the organization's goals and the willingness they have to work towards these goals (Manetje and Martins, 2009).

According to Meyer and Allen (as cited in McMahan, 2007), organizational employees' commitment has three main aspects: affective, continuance, and normative commitments. Affective commitment is defined as the emotional and sentimental attachment an individual has towards an organization. It is also considered as the level to which employees identify themselves with the organization and its goals to maintain their membership (Modway *et al.*, as cited in Azeem, 2010). The characteristics of the affective commitment include three elements: the belief and the acceptance of the organization's values and objectives; the willingness to work towards the organization's goals, and the aim to maintain the relationship with the organization (Porter *et al.*, as cited in Ismail, 2012). The continuance commitment is linked with the costs related to the alternatives to leave the organization. In other words, the employees remain in the organization because the alternatives are inexistent or not certain. Concerning the normative commitment is the moral obligation an individual has to remain in the organization. So, the employees are loyal and consecrated to the organization as a duty and obligation (Ismail, 2012).

Employee commitment in this context remains important because of its potential effect on employees' identification with the organization's goals, the desire to commitment, particularly in the area of work, has been analysed from several perspectives (Martin and O'Laughlin, 1984; Morrow, 1983; Mowday *et al.*, 1982). It has served as both a dependent variable for antecedents such as age, tenure, gender and education (Ferris and Aranya, 1983; Hunt *et al.*, 1985; Luthans *et al.*, 1985), and as a predictor of various outcomes such as turnover (Rusbult and Farrell, 1983), intention to leave (Ferris and Aranya, 1983) and absenteeism retain membership with the organization and the level of effort exerted (Meyer and Allen, 1997; Hartman and Bambacas, 2000; Jaramillo *et al.*, 2005; Van Breugel *et al.*, 2005).

Organizations are intended to have more highly committed workforce, because the research results show that employee commitment leads to important outcomes such as decreased turnover, higher motivation, higher organization citizenship behaviour and organizational support (Kwon and Banks, 2004). Managers could benefit from understanding the predictors of committed manpower because they can initiate the interventions when the problem exists. They can adopt, for example, the appropriate leadership behaviour in order to improve the level of employee commitment and, in turn, the levels of job satisfaction and job performance (Yousef, 2000). Research shows that understanding employee commitment can provide insight into how employee commitment is related to the intentions to leave. The turnover is always costly to the organizations in all sectors given the large investment made in the selection, training and development of personnel (Stallworth, 2004, 2003). Also there are

some findings that any effort to improve employee commitment is beneficial in lowering stress levels in the job concerning areas such as staffing and the perceived pressure of the job (Savery and Syme, 1996).

Measures of Employee Commitment

Affective Commitment

Affective commitment is defined as the emotional attachment, identification, and involvement that an employee has with his or her organization (Aydin *et al.* 2011). It is the positive emotional attachment that employees feel for the organization because they see their goals and values to be congruent with those of the organization. Meyer and Allen (1997), note that employees retain membership out of choice and this is their commitment to the organization. Employees, who are affectively committed, strongly identify with the goals of the organization and desire to remain a part of the organization. These employees commit to the organization because they want to (Aydin *et al.* 2011). The concept of affective commitment is linked to the idea that strongly committed persons identify with, are involved in, and enjoy membership in an organization (Thuy & Van, 2020).

It is an emotional state where individuals identify themselves with their organization, interact with their organization and are happy about being members of their organization (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019). It is closely related to emotional reactions to business environment and is concerned with more dedication to work, and satisfaction with the colleagues, their workplace and the profession (Balay, 2012). It refers to employees' integration into their organizations. Those who have strong affective commitment become a member of the organization not because they need it but because they regard themselves as part of the organization and have adopted its goals. Employees who feel this kind of commitment demonstrate high fidelity to their organizations and volunteer to make more effort when need arises. Employees develop commitment to their work as long as they adopt the goals and targets of the organization (Bayram, 2005). All kinds of commitment in fact bind employees to the organization but the most effective commitment is the one that has an effective dimension. Affective commitment, which leads to a positive attitude and behavior towards the organization, is the best form of employee commitment to organization (Astuti & Ingsih, 2019). For, employees with high levels of affective commitment remain in the organization because they want to do so and make huge efforts towards the goals of the organization. These employees are loyal employees who have devoted themselves to the organization. When necessary, they volunteer to assume additional responsibilities and display a positive attitude towards their job and their coworkers (Doğan and Demiral, 2009). Employees who have affective commitment stay with the organization because they want it (Meyer and Allen, 1997).

Normative Commitment

Normative commitment is the commitment that people believe they have to the organization or their feeling of obligation to their workplace. It refers to the employee's feeling of duty, loyalty or obligation to the organization (Unal, 2019). These feelings may derive from many sources. For example, the organization may have invested resources in training an employee who then feels a 'moral' obligation to put forth effort on the job and stay with the organization to 'repay the debt.' It may also reflect an internalized norm, developed before the person joins the organization through family or other socialization processes, that one should be loyal to one's organization (Aydin *et al.* 2011).

In normative commitment an individual is willing to stay within an organization and contribute to an organization to correspond with a group norm (Dixit & Bhati, 2012). Affective, continuance, and normative commitment are components of organizational commitment rather than types because employees could have varying degrees of all three (Meyer & Allen, 1991). In other words, the three components are not mutually exclusive: an employee

can simultaneously be committed to the organization in an affective, normative, and continuance sense, at varying levels of intensity.

The above idea led Meyer and Herscovitch (2001) to argue that at any point in time, an employee has a commitment profile that reflects high or low levels of all three of these components, and that different profiles have different effects on workplace behaviour such as job performance, absenteeism, and the chance that they will quit. Meyer, Allen, and Smith (1993) argue that the three components of commitment are a psychological state that either characterizes the employee's relationship with the organization or has the implications to affect whether the employee will continue staying with the organization.

Normative commitment reflects an employee's obligation to stay in his organization (Bryant et al, 2007). Organizational culture, rewards, punishments, and employee autonomy play a vital role in deciding the level of normative commitment (Meyer & Allen, 1997; Chang, 2002; Haar & Spell, 2004, and Sharma & Sinha, 2015). Normative commitment in the field of management has been described as the obligation to remain in a particular organization (Bryant et al., 2007; Lumley et al., 2011; Yildiz, 2018). Employees in this type of commitment remain with their organization because they feel that they should to do so for moral reasons, not because they want or need to (Yildiz, 2019).

Continuance Commitment

Continuance commitment is the willingness to remain in an organization because of the investment that the employee has with “non-transferable” investments. Non-transferable investments may include retirement, relationships with other employees, and other things that are special to the organization (Obeng & Ugboro, 2003). Continuance commitment also includes factors such as years of employment or benefits that the employee may receive that are unique to the organization (Imamoglu, Ince, Turkcan & Atakay, 2019).

The main factor that influences continuance commitment is the maintenance in the organization (Yalçın & Iplik, 2005). Continuance commitment emanates from the disadvantages that an employee will face when he leaves the organization (Aydin *et al.* 2011). In general, continuance commitment depicts an employee's assessment of whether the costs of leaving the organization are greater than the cost of staying. That is, the need to stay with the organization based on the costs of leaving or a sense that available comparable alternatives are limited.

It is related to the performance required to keep a job and the costs encountered by leaving the organization (Bell-Ellis et al., 2015). Continuance commitment develops when an employee recognizes that he or she stands to lose investment in the organization, or realize that no alternatives exists other than remaining in the organization (Yousaf, Sanders, & Abbas 2015). These investments include physical, cognitive, and emotional investments such as salary and benefits, retirement plans, skills, social relationship, and lost opportunities (Lambert, Hogan, & Keena, 2015). Another classification of investments made in the organization includes financial investments such as pay, benefits, job security, and retirement money; and non-financial investments such as status and friendship with colleagues (Zayas-Ortiz, Rosario, Marquez, & Gruñeiro, 2015). As such, the employee bonds with the organization because he/she must do so and is compelled to do so (Lambert et al., 2019).

Cynicism and Employee Commitment

Wanous et al. (2000) concluded that individuals with cynical feelings have lower organizational commitment. In the same way, employees with the high level of commitment were observed to be less likely to exhibit cynical behavior. Pitre (2004) found that there is a relationship between organizational commitment and organizational cynicism in United States Naval Academy and also a relation between decision-making and risk-taking is documented as well. Naus (2007) concluded that employees with organizational cynicism have a decrease in

organizational commitment, motivation and job satisfaction. Rubin et al.(2009)found negative relationship between leaders 'level of cynicism towards organizational change and organizational commitment. In another study, Barnes (2010) stated that employees with cynical attitudes exhibit lower commitment and it has referred that sometimes cynicism may have a positive impact on the organizations. Another research done by Altınöz et al. (2011), relationship between organizational commitment and organizational cynicism, perceived by hotel employees was examined. It was stated that when organizational commitment level of employee increases, they exhibit less cynical attitudes; likewise, employees with cynical attitudes become less committed. Findik and Eryesil (2012) examined the effect of the employees' cynical attitudes towards changes on their organizational commitment. A negative relationship between organizational cynicism and organizational commitment was documented in the research. Balıkcıoğlu (2013) investigated the relationship between organizational cynicism and organizational commitment in hospitality businesses in Antalya. Research results indicated that, employees exhibit low organizational cynicism and high organizational commitment. Ergen (2015) found similar results with previous studies and stated that organizational commitment decreases when organizational cynicism increases. The relationship between organizational cynicisms is highly connected by notions mentioned and organizational commitment is object of interest. Philosophical change in administration policy from control to commitment in last 1980's and in the beginning of 1990's provides a basis to the foundation of the organizational commitment (İnce and Gül, 2005). According to Guetzkov, who study on commitment notion firstly, commitment is a psychological situation which makes person ready for a certain though, person or group, (Yazıcıoğlu and Topaloğlu, 2009) and which characterizes the organizational communication and which has effect on continuity of organizational membership (Meyer and Allen, 1997).

According to the results of the research by Uysa and Yıldız (2014), organizational cynicism has predicted "adaptation" dimension in high level whereas it has predicted "identification" dimension in medium and "internalization" dimension in low level. Results indicate the meaning and significance of organizational cynicism on organizational commitment and organizational commitment is decreasing while level of organizational cynicism in schools is increasing. When organizational commitment having positive effect on employee performance, that Uysa and Yıldız (2014) have stated this effect as considerable rate like 20%, and offering opportunity to being concentrated on work by disposing of negative thoughts like resignation and absenteeism are taken into account (Bayram, 2005; Kalağan, 2009; Polat and Meydan, 2010; Güzel, Perçin and Tükeltürk, 2010), positive and effective communication between teachers and administrators must be created in order to reduce the levels of organizational cynicism in schools and its effects. Administrators should struggle for reducing of in appreciativeness of the teachers from own schools and changing critical attitudes and behaviors to positive; should appreciate teachers' efforts, award teachers' successes and make them feel precious for school. Besides, leadership styles reducing cynicism is determined (Doğan and Uğurlu, 2014; Mamatoğlu, 2010; Mete and Serin, 2015; Tak and Çiftçioğlu, 2008). Thus, teachers making sacrifice for objectives and future of own schools and integrating with schools can be ensured. It is important that administrators should be consistent in statements and actions and should create an atmosphere with highly reliable background in that process (Altınöz and Çöp, 2012). Teachers relying on administrators will be effective on avoiding cynical behaviors.

Aslan and Eren (2014) as negative effects distinguish indifference, withdrawal, separation, hopelessness, distrust, and suspicion. Cynicism can be expressed by alienation and negative feelings towards a particular person, group, ideology or society, while the employees' negative attitude can be characterized as an inclination towards tendentious disappointment, critical and poor commitment. Thus, on the one hand, organizational cynicism has a

negative impact on organizational commitment by reducing it (Bernerth et al., 2007; Saleem et al., 2018), on the other hand, we see that both phenomena can affect both loyalty, and lesser commitment. As demonstrated in the study conducted by Dobbs and Do (2018), there is a link between toxic leadership and organizational cynicism. That is, persons who have traits of “toxic leaders” are more negative about their organization, demonstrating their cynical attitude.

From the foregoing discussions, we hereby hypothesize thus;

H_{0:1} there is no significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and affective commitment in selected foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

H_{0:2} there is no significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and normative commitment in selected foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

H_{0:3} there is no significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and continuance commitment in selected foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

METHODS

The research design is the general plan, the structure and the strategy to carry out an investigation. It refers to the specification of methods and procedures to acquire the necessary information to solve the problem. According to Burns and Grove (2003), the purpose of research design is to achieve greater control of the study and to improve the validity of the study by examining the research problem. The study used correlational research design. A population is the accessible components of the census normally established in numbers (Baridam, 2001). According to Manufactures Association of Nigeria (MAN), there are fourteen foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt. For this study, our population is the total number of employees in foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt. A total population for the fourteen companies is one thousand and ninety-three (1093) workers.

The researcher adopted the Taro Yamene’s formula in determining the sample size. $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$

Therefore, sample size

$$n = \frac{1093}{1 + 1093(0.05)^2}$$

$$= 292$$

Table 1: The sample size distribution of questionnaire based on proportional allocation

S/N	NAMES OF THE COMPANIES	WORKERS	SAMPLE SIZE
1	Rivers Vegetable Oil	56	15
2	White Diamond Salt Limited	53	14
3	Multipro Enterprises	179	48
4	Crown Flour Mills Limited (Olam)	58	15
5	Checkers Enterprises	49	13
6	Pabod Breweries Limited	165	44
7	Seven-up Bottling Company Limited	54	14
8	Nigerian Bottling Company	177	47
9	Adietz Enterprises	29	8
10	Mac Canon Industrial Ltd.	31	9
11	PH flour mills ltd	43	12

12	Rossy endeavours Ltd	41	11		
13	Royal Salt Ltd	75	20		
14	Pure Flour Mills Ltd	83	22		
		1093		292	

Source: Research Desk, 2020

The proportional allocation of population has the formula for its distribution as below:

$$\text{Distribution of sample size} = \frac{\text{Group population}}{\text{Total population}} * \text{Sample size}$$

Table 2. Response Rate

S/N	NAMES OF THE COMPANIES	DISTRIBUTED QUESTIONNAIRE	RETRIEVED QUESTIONNAIRE	Not Retrieved	Wrongly Filled
1	Rivers Vegetable Oil	15	15	-	-
2	White Diamond Salt Limited	14	14	-	-
3	Multipro Enterprises	48	44	3	1
4	Crown Flour Mills Limited (Olam)	15	15	-	-
5	Checkers Enterprises	13	13	-	-
6	Pabod Breweries Limited	44	39	5	-
7	Seven-up Bottling Company Limited	14	14	-	-
8	Nigerian Bottling Company	47	40	5	2
9	Adietz Enterprises	8	8	-	-
10	Mac Canon Industrial Ltd.	9	9	-	-
11	PH flour mills ltd	12	11	1	-
12	Rossy endeavours Ltd	11	11	-	-
<hr/>					
13	Royal Salt Ltd ss	20	18	1	1
14	Pure Flour Mills Ltd	22	19	3	-
		292	270	18	4

Source: Research Desk, 2020

The response rate for the distributed questionnaire indicated that out of the two hundred and ninetytwo (292) distributed questionnaire two hundred and seventy (270) were retrieved and used. This amounted to about 92.5% of the distributed questionnaire.

The reliability of the research instrument was tested through the Cronbach Alpha coefficient, hence, only the items that return Alpha value of 0.7 and above were considered reliable. Nunnaly (1978) stated that the reliability of the data after testing by Cronbach Alpha, should require a reliability score of more than 70% i.e > 0.7. Therefore, from the obtained Cronbach Alpha for the items in the research questionnaire, it was clear that the structured questions are reliable.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS Bivariate Analysis (Correlation)

The essence is to analyze how cognitive cynicism relates to the measures of employee commitment. There was analysis of cognitive cynicism with each of the measures (affective, normative and continuance commitments) respectively. The Spearman Rank Order Correlation was adopted as the statistical tool to test the formulated hypotheses through the statistical package for social sciences software (SPSS) version 22.0 to establish the relationships. The correlation coefficients range from -1.00 to +1.00.

Table 3. Cognitive Cynicism and Affective Commitment

		Correlations	
		Cognitive	
Spearman's rho Cognitive	Correlation	1.000	
	Coefficient	-.533*	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041	
	N	270	270
Affective	Correlation	-.533*	1.000
	Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041	
	N	270	270

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2019

H01: There is no significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and affective commitment in the foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

The above table shows a negative and significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and affective commitment with a rho value of -0.533. This indicates that there is a 53.3% explanation of the relationship between both variables, while 46.7% are explained by other variables not considered in this relationship. However, this statement is true as the level of significance of 0.041 is less than 0.05, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and its alternative form accepted. This states that there is significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and affective commitment in the foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

Table 4. Cognitive Cynicism and Normative Commitment Correlations

	Cognitive	Normative
Spearman's rho Cognitive Correlation	1.000	-.575*
Coefficient		

Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.025
N	270	270
Normative Correlation Coefficient	-.575*	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	.025	.
<u>N</u>	<u>270</u>	270

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2019

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and normative commitment in the foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

The above table shows a negative and significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and normative commitment with a rho value of -0.575. This indicates that there is a 57.5% explanation of the relationship between both variables, while 42.5% are explained by other variables not considered in this relationship. However, this statement is true as the level of significance of 0.025 is less than 0.05, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and its alternative form accepted. This states that there is significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and normative commitment in the foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

Table 5. Cognitive Cynicism and Continuance Commitment Correlations

			Continuance
			ce
	Correlation	Cognitive	-.642**
Spearman's rho	Coefficient	1.000	
Cognitive	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.010
	N	270	270
Continuance	Correlation	-.642**	1.000
ce	Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.010	.
	<u>N</u>	<u>270</u>	270

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2019

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and continuance commitment in the foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

The above table shows a negative and significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and continuance commitment with a rho value of -0.642. This indicates that there is a 64.2% explanation of the relationship between both variables, while 35.8% are explained by other variables not considered in this relationship. However, this statement is true as the level of significance of 0.010 is less than 0.05, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and its alternative form accepted. This states that there is significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and continuance commitment in the foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS Association between Cognitive Cynicism and Affective Commitment

There is a negative and significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and affective commitment in the foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

This refers to lack of sincerity, honesty, and justice in the organization, where cognitive cynicism is accessible when staff feels that their corporation does not esteem their endeavours or care about every one of them, and therefore may be unlikely to make their best efforts for their corporation (Rehan, Iqbal, Fatima & Nawabl, 2017). Openness by organizations if perceived by workers as not being present is argued to result in negative affective and emotional reactions, escalated levels of stress, and burnout. As argued in the norm of reciprocity, unmet expectations regarding the decision making process and personal interactions lead individuals to feel increasingly higher levels of frustration and psychological distress (Tepper, 2001), which in turn result in workforce no commitment. The sense of openness alleviates the detrimental effects of high job demands. Consistent with these premises, the literature also provides empirical evidence indicating that those employees perceiving organizational injustice are more likely to experience burnout (Van Yperen, Buunk, & Schaufeli, 1992; Van Horn et al., 1999). Likewise, the existence of openness is found to be a valuable factor for coping with stress (Kroon, van de Voorde, & van Veldhoven, 2009) and preventing burnout (Noblet & Rodwell, 2009) which decreases one's commitment in the organization.

Workers facing cognitive cynicism think that principles are often sacrificed for expedience, and that duality, guile, and personal interest are common in their firms (Rehan, Iqbal, Fatima & Nawabl, 2017). Bernerth, Armenakis, Field & Walker (2007) found that employees' perceptions of cognitive cynicism are negatively associated with organizational commitment (Bernerth, Armenakis, Field & Walker, 2007). Deriving from the aforementioned relationship, it might be assumed that workers' perception of fairness regarding workplace outcomes or processes might have effects on their stress levels. Such that when workers evaluate organizational practices as being unfair, their tendency to feel incompatible becomes prevalent. Thus:

- i. Openness influences compatibility among the workforce with organizational goals and objectives which decreases cognitive cynicism.
- ii. Decreased cognitive cynicism results in increased affective commitment in an organization.

Association between Cognitive Cynicism and Normative Commitment

There is a negative and significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and normative commitment in the foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

When employees perceive to be neglected by the organization's system, they have a higher tendency to feel out of sync with its values (Brom, Buruck, Horvath, Richter, & Leiter, 2015). Supporting this theory's assertion, previous studies report that insufficient rewards and lack of recognition decreases employees' resilience to burnout (Chappell & Novak, 1992; Maslanka, 1996). More specifically, it is reported that individuals who have experienced an imbalance in efforts and rewards are more likely to feel inequality than those who have not (Bakker, Kilmeri, Sigrist, & Schaufeli, 2000; Frenkel, Li, & Restubog, 2012), and as such tends to not feel committed to the organization. Similarly, Abraham indicated that cognitive cynicism reduces the performance in the organization (Abraham, 2000).

Morgan (2005) posits that cognitive cynicism which is the belief that emerges with negative emotions such as anger, condescension, and condemnation that the organization is not honest.

These cynics believe that organizational practices are not fair, honest, and sincere, and they don't trust their organizations (Brandes and Das, 2006). In this regard, the belief based on that there is unprincipled practices in

organization has role on this cognitive approach (Pelit and Pelit, 2014). Cognitive cynicism shapes cynical attitudes or behaviors (Delken, 2004) leading to no commitment. Thus; In high levels of cognitive cynicism within the workforce of an organization, there is little or no level of commitment.

Association between Cognitive Cynicism and Continuance Commitment

There is a negative and significant relationship between cognitive cynicism and continuance commitment in the foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.

Effective communication is necessary to build high trust and commitment levels in the organization (Shockley-Zalabak et al., 2010). Cynicism was reduced with open and honest communication, and resulted in the ability to better collaborate and engage in constructive disagreement (Shockley-Zalabak et al., 2010) which results in maximum cooperation. Openness and honesty were about clear, timely and credible communication channels. Employees must feel safe and free to address problems in the workplace by collaborating freely and building high trust levels facilitates high levels of commitment. An environment with high levels of cynicism could result in much uncertainty regarding performance, supervisor instructions and suspicion regarding the intent of management communications. Such an environment could not contribute to employee commitment.

Gajda (2004) proposed that communication focused on networking, partnering, merging, and unifying. This is especially helpful in remembering that higher level cooperative work involves the merging into a single identity while maintaining past identities. Frey et al. (2006) proposed that the interactions among workers involve networking, coordination, coalition and collaboration.

Employee willingness to exchange ideas, even when the employee's ideas ran counter to prevailing thought, displayed an open atmosphere and was a key factor related to trust (Thomas, Zolin & Hartman, 2009) and reduces the level of sentiments brewed in the mind of the employee. This reduced negative sentiment has a cushioning effect on cynicism and amplifies the longing in the heart of the worker to want to remain with the organization.

CONCLUSION

The following conclusion was evident;

- i. Cognitive cynicism in foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt has a negative and significant correlation on affective commitment.
- ii. Cognitive cynicism influences normative commitment negatively in foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt.
- iii. Cognitive cynicism does have a negative and significant association to continuance commitment in foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt. Recommendations

The following specific recommendations are made based on the findings of this study:

- i. Cognitive cynicism in foods, beverages and tobacco companies in Port Harcourt is a major setback to organizational success and performance, and as such if eliminated will help the workers to build an emotional attachment for their work and the organization at large.
- ii. Cognitive cynicism psychologically affects workers, therefore, if organizations can introduce social and educational empowerment programs, these will make the workers feel indebted to the organization and become committed.
- iii. Organizations need to develop measures that inculcate openness in decision making processes as a means to eradicate cognitive cynicism in order to have workers that will find it difficult to leave the organization.

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